

Analytic Code

#Install packages

```
install.packages('jmv')
```

#Load packages

```
library(jmv)
```

#Create sociodemographic characteristics plus histograms

```
jmv::descriptives(  
  data = data,  
  vars = vars(Alter, BMI),  
  hist = TRUE,  
  dens = TRUE,  
  skew = TRUE,  
  kurt = TRUE)
```

#Check reliability/internal consistency

#reliability T1_BD

```
jmv::reliability(  
  data = data,  
  vars = vars(BD18_01, BD18_02, BD18_03, BD18_04, BD18_05, BD18_06, BD18_07, BD18_08,  
  BD18_09))
```

#reliability T2_BD

```
jmv::reliability(  
  data = data,  
  vars = vars(BD09_01, BD09_02, BD09_03, BD10_01, BD16_01, BD11_01))
```

#reliability T1_BA

```
jmv::reliability(  
  data = data,  
  vars = vars(BA07_01, BA07_02, BA07_03, BA07_04, BA07_05, BA07_06, BA07_07, BA07_08,  
  BA07_09, BA07_10))
```

#reliability T2_BA

```
jmv::reliability(  
  data = data,  
  vars = vars(BA08_01, BA08_02, BA08_03, BA08_04, BA08_05, BA08_06, BA08_07, BA08_08,  
  BA08_09, BA08_10))
```

#Adjust scale levels: Form Factors

```
data$Gruppe <- factor(data$Gruppe)
```

#Describe sample by group

```
jmv::descriptives(  
  formula = T1_BD + T2_BD + T1_BA + T2_BA + SISE + BMI + Alter + BiC ~ Gruppe,  
  data = data)
```

#Correlation matrix

```
jmv::corrMatrix(  
  data = data,  
  vars = vars(T1_BD, T2_BD, T1_BA, T2_BA, SISE, BMI, Alter, BiC),  
  flag = TRUE,  
  ci = TRUE)
```

#Create boxplots

```
jmv::descriptives(  
  data = data,  
  vars = vars(T1_BD, T2_BD, T1_BA, T2_BA, Alter, BMI, SISE, BiC),  
  box = TRUE,  
  violin = TRUE,  
  dot = TRUE)
```

#Examination of the conditions

#ANOVA for checking the independence of covariates and group

```
jmv::anovaOneW(  
  formula = T1_BA + T1_BD + Alter + BMI + SISE + BiC ~ Gruppe,  
  data = data,  
  eqv = TRUE)
```

#Interaction terms Body Appreciation (homogeneity of regression slopes)

```
jmv::ancova(  
  formula = T2_BA ~ Gruppe + T1_BA + SISE + BMI + Alter + Gruppe:T1_BA + Gruppe:SISE +  
  Gruppe:BMI + Gruppe:Alter,  
  data = data,  
  effectSize = c("eta", "partEta"),  
  modelTest = TRUE,  
  homo = TRUE)
```

#Interaction terms Body Dissatisfaction (homogeneity of regression slopes)

```
jmv::ancova(  
  formula = T2_BD ~ T1_BD + SISE + BMI + Alter + Gruppe + Gruppe:T1_BD + Gruppe:SISE +  
  Gruppe:BMI + Gruppe:Alter,  
  data = data,  
  effectSize = c("eta", "partEta"),  
  modelTest = TRUE,  
  homo = TRUE)
```

#Manipulation Checks

#Manipulation Check 1: ANOVA for BAO_Index

```
jmv::anovaOneW(  
  formula = BAO_Index ~ Gruppe,  
  data = data,  
  welchs = FALSE,  
  fishers = TRUE,  
  desc = TRUE,  
  eqv = TRUE)
```

#Manipulation Check 1: ANOVA for BAP_Index

```
jmv::anovaOneW(  
  formula = BAP_Index ~ Gruppe,  
  data = data,  
  desc = TRUE,  
  eqv = TRUE,  
  phMethod = "gamesHowell",  
  phTest = TRUE,  
  phFlag = TRUE)
```

#Manipulation Check 2 in controlgroup

```
jmv::ttestOneS(  
  data = data_control,  
  vars = vars(VG_BAP, VG_BAO),  
  testValue = 4,  
  meanDiff = TRUE,  
  ci = TRUE,  
  effectSize = TRUE,  
  ciES = TRUE)
```

#Manipulation Check 2 in BAP-Group

```
jmv::ttestOneS(  
  data = data_BAP,  
  vars = vars(VG_BAP, VG_BAO),  
  testValue = 4,  
  meanDiff = TRUE,  
  ci = TRUE,  
  effectSize = TRUE,  
  ciES = TRUE)
```

#Manipulation Check 2 in BAO-Group

```
jmv::ttestOneS(  
  data = data_BAO,  
  vars = vars(VG_BAP, VG_BAO),  
  testValue = 4,  
  meanDiff = TRUE,  
  ci = TRUE,  
  effectSize = TRUE,  
  ciES = TRUE)
```

#Main Analysis: Body Appreciation

#ANCOVA Body Appreciation

```
jmv::ancova(  
  formula = T2_BA ~ Gruppe + T1_BA + SISE + BMI + Alter,  
  data = data,  
  effectSize = c("eta", "partEta"),  
  modelTest = TRUE,  
  homo = TRUE,  
  emMeans = ~ Gruppe,  
  ciWidthEmm = 95,  
  emmTables = TRUE)
```

#Post-hoc Tests for Body Appreciation

```
jmv::ancova(  
  formula = T2_BA ~ Gruppe + T1_BA + SISE + Alter + BMI,  
  data = data,  
  effectSize = c("eta", "partEta"),  
  modelTest = TRUE,  
  homo = TRUE,  
  postHoc = ~ Gruppe,  
  postHocCorr = "bonf",  
  postHocES = "d",  
  postHocEsCi = TRUE,  
  emMeans = ~ Gruppe,  
  ciWidthEmm = 95,  
  emmTables = TRUE)
```

#ANCOVA Body Appreciation without covariates (incl. Post-Hoc test)

```
jmv::ancova(  
  formula = T2_BA ~ Gruppe + T1_BA,  
  data = data,  
  effectSize = c("eta", "partEta"),  
  modelTest = TRUE,  
  homo = TRUE,  
  postHoc = ~ Gruppe,  
  postHocCorr = "bonf",  
  postHocES = "d",  
  postHocEsCi = TRUE,  
  emMeans = ~ Gruppe,  
  ciWidthEmm = 95,  
  emmTables = TRUE)
```

#Main Analysis: Body Dissatisfaction

#ANCOVA Body Dissatisfaction

```
jmv::ancova(  
  formula = T2_BD ~ Gruppe + T1_BD + SISE + BMI + Alter,  
  data = data,  
  effectSize = c("eta", "partEta"),  
  modelTest = TRUE,  
  homo = TRUE,  
  emMeans = ~ Gruppe,  
  emmPlotData = TRUE,  
  ciWidthEmm = 95,  
  emmTables = TRUE)
```

#ANCOVA Body Dissatisfaction without covariates

```
jmv::ancova(  
  formula = T2_BD ~ Gruppe + T1_BD,  
  data = data,  
  effectSize = c("eta", "partEta"),  
  modelTest = TRUE,  
  homo = TRUE,  
  emMeans = ~ Gruppe,  
  emmPlotData = TRUE,
```

```
ciWidthEmm = 95,  
emmTables = TRUE)
```

#Exploratory Analysis

#Interaction terms Body Dissatisfaction with additional covariate: BiC

```
jmv::ancova(  
  formula = T2_BD ~ T1_BD + SISE + BMI + Alter + BiC + Gruppe + Gruppe:T1_BD + Gruppe:SISE +  
  Gruppe:BMI + Gruppe:Alter + Gruppe:BiC,  
  data = data,  
  effectSize = c("eta", "partEta"),  
  modelTest = TRUE,  
  homo = TRUE)
```

#ANCOVA Body Dissatisfaction with additional covariate: BiC

```
jmv::ancova(  
  formula = T2_BD ~ Gruppe + T1_BD + SISE + BMI + Alter + BiC,  
  data = data,  
  effectSize = c("eta", "partEta"),  
  modelTest = TRUE,  
  homo = TRUE,  
  emMeans = ~ Gruppe,  
  ciWidthEmm = 95,  
  emmTables = TRUE)
```

#Interaction terms Body Appreciation with additional covariate: BiC

```
jmv::ancova(  
  formula = T2_BA ~ Gruppe + T1_BA + SISE + BMI + Alter + BiC + Gruppe:T1_BA + Gruppe:SISE +  
  Gruppe:BMI + Gruppe:Alter + Gruppe:BiC,  
  data = data,  
  effectSize = c("eta", "partEta"),  
  modelTest = TRUE,  
  homo = TRUE)
```

#ANCOVA Body Appreciation with additional covariate: BiC (incl. Post-Hoc test)

```
jmv::ancova(  
  formula = T2_BA ~ Gruppe + T1_BA + SISE + BMI + Alter + BiC,  
  data = data,  
  effectSize = c("eta", "partEta"),  
  modelTest = TRUE,  
  homo = TRUE,  
  postHoc = ~ Gruppe,  
  postHocCorr = "bonf",  
  postHocES = "d",  
  postHocEsCi = TRUE,  
  emMeans = ~ Gruppe,  
  ciWidthEmm = 95,  
  emmTables = TRUE)
```